

Probabilistic Sensitivity Studies of a Multiscale Model for Bonded Composite Pi-joint Performance

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- I. Background and Motivation: Process-to-Performance Simulation Framework for Bonded Composites
- II. Homogenized Pi-joint Model Approach
 1. Mesoscale Textile Model
 2. Macroscale, Homogenized Pi-joint Model
- III. Probabilistic Analysis and Uncertainty Quantification
- IV. Global Sensitivity Analysis Results and Discussion
- V. Summary

- ▶ **Bonded composite primary structures for advanced aircraft systems**
 - ▶ **Advantages:** (1) reduced weight, (2) reduced part count, and (3) improved performance
 - ▶ **Challenges:** (1) limited software tools for design and analysis, (2) impact of uncertainties and manufacturing defects not well understood², and (3) fasteners used because bond is not trusted

- ▶ **OPPERA Program: OMC (Organic Matrix Composite) Process-to-Performance Evaluation, Research, and Analysis**
 - ▶ **Program objective:** Develop validated process-to-performance (P2P) methods to predict static response and fatigue life of bonded composite structures → reduce cost and schedule impacts during certification
 - ▶ **Demonstration article:** bonded composite pi-preform joint
 - ▶ **Study objective:** develop engineering tool for assessing structural response of bonded composite pi-joints under uncertainty

- ▶ **Research question:** What is the relationship between textile architecture and the structural response of the Pi-joint?

Pi-joint Demonstration Article¹

[1] Flansburg et al., AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, 2009.

[2] Omairey et al., SN Applied Sciences, 2021.

▶ **Multiscale framework for process-to-performance (P2P) modeling** → mesoscale fiber architecture to macroscale component response

▶ **Flexible** → multiple paths through the framework to capture various phenomena and allow for flexibility in solution fidelity

▶ **Predictive Capability**

1. Fiber bed compaction and relaxation
2. Material properties, residual stresses, and porosity evolution during cure
3. Damage evolution at mesoscale and macroscale
4. Final part capability

OPPERA Homogenized Pi-joint Model Approach

- ▶ **VTMS simulates the morphology of the textile RVE after weaving**
 - ▶ Digital chains represent bundles of fibers within the tow → used to achieve tow fiber volume fraction without discretely modeling every fiber in the tow
 - ▶ Final architecture based on Fiber relaxation and compaction steps
 - ▶ Surface smoothing and volume-based approaches to generate the tow geometry for FEA
- ▶ **BSAM simulates the mechanical and fracture response of the textile RVE composite**
 - ▶ The independent mesh method is used for meshing fiber tows and matrix
 - ▶ Employs periodic cluster method (PCM)³ to address limitations associated with non-conforming mesh for side-to-side
 - ▶ Calculate the effective elastic properties from 6 loading state
- ▶ **Abaqus simulates the structural response of the Pi-joint**
 - ▶ Over 100 geometric, mechanical, and fracture parameters in parametric pi-joint model
 - ▶ Linear elastic material properties for pi-preform, web, and skin and cohesive zone model for adhesive bond

[3] Hoos et al. AIAA SciTech, 2022.

OPPERA Textile Homogenization (VTMS + BSAM)

- ▶ **Conforming mesh is an issue for complicated textile geometries**
- ▶ **The independent mesh method (IMM) is used to address this meshing issue**
 - ▶ Combination of direct meshing of the tows and a voxel-based methodology within the matrix
 - ▶ Integration enrichment for connectivity between the tows and matrix
 - ▶ Limitation: requires node-to-node periodicity on opposing sides of the finite element mesh
- ▶ **IMM node-to-node periodicity limitation is addressed by periodic cluster method (PCM)³**
 - ▶ Utilizes additional plates at the edges of the RVE that connect via penalty connection
 - ▶ Displacements between opposing periodic clusters are tied together and properties are tailored to provide very little additional stiffness to the model
 - ▶ Satisfies node-to-node periodicity requirement and allows RVE mesh to be non-conforming side-to-side
- ▶ **Calculate the 9 effective elastic properties from 6 loading states**

Findings from Previous Study⁴

$$COV = \frac{\text{standard deviation}}{\text{mean}}$$

- ▶ **Largest sources of uncertainty**
 - ▶ Tow XY Poisson's ratio ($\nu_{12,tow}$): **8.5% COV**
 - ▶ Warp tow fiber volume fraction ($V_{f,warp}$): **6.2% COV**
 - ▶ Matrix tensile modulus (E_m): **6.0 % COV**
 - ▶ Fill tow fiber volume fraction ($V_{f,fill}$): **5.1% COV**
 - ▶ All other mesoscale material properties: **< 5% COV**
- ▶ **Each of the nine homogenized properties was primarily sensitive to uncertainty in the tow V_f and/or $\nu_{12,tow}$**
- ▶ **Current mesoscale models do not account of intra- or inter-tow spatial variability in tow V_f**
 - ▶ One $V_{f,warp}$ and one $V_{f,fill}$ value describe all tows in the model
 - ▶ Not accounting for spatial variability yields overly conservative results

▶ **The value of the sensitivity analyses would be more impactful if mesoscale models were linked to macroscale analyses**

- ▶ **Proposed future work from previous study**
 - ▶ Additional characterization of $\nu_{12,tow}$ and $V_{f,warp}$
 - ▶ Model spatial variability in tow V_f for more realistic simulations
 - ▶ Link mesoscale textile model with macroscale pi-joint model

[4] Kirby et al. AIAA SciTech, 2022.

▶ **Parametric model of the pi-joint in Abaqus⁵**

- ▶ Over 100 geometric, mechanical, and fracture parameters
- ▶ Linear elastic material properties for pi-preform, web, and skin
- ▶ Cohesive zone model for adhesive bond
- ▶ Predicts stresses in pi-preform → does not model damage in preform
- ▶ Simulates pure pull-off (PO), pure lateral bend (LB), and combined pull-off plus lateral bend (PO+LB) loading configurations
- ▶ Currently developing capabilities for pure shear (PS) loading configuration

▶ **Focus of this study is predicting the lateral bend (LB) response of the pi-joint**

- ▶ Only have validated mesoscale model for pi-preform leg architecture
- ▶ LB response is more sensitive to leg architecture than PO due to bending in the leg
- ▶ In this study, the pi-preform base and leg are assumed to have same architecture

▶ **During LB pi-joint testing, failures have been observed in the adhesive (Mode I fracture) and the pi-preform radius**

Predicted Adhesive Failure During Lateral Bend Testing

[5] Kirby et al. AIAA SciTech, 2023.

- ▶ **Failure of the pi-preform in the radius between base and leg is a concern (failure modes 1 & 3)**
 - ▶ The model does not capture pi-preform damage, so max stress & strain in this region are the quantities of interest
 - ▶ Future work could involve using homogenized strength or strain-based criteria to predict damage onset in preform
- ▶ **Macroscale model responses of interest**
 - ▶ Maximum load and stiffness (slope) from force-displacement curve
 - ▶ Maximum stress in pi-preform radius at maximum load → associated with failure modes 1 & 3
- ▶ **What is the impact of uncertainty in mesoscale properties on uncertainty in the predicted lateral bend response?**

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▶ NESSUS® probabilistic analysis software

- ▶ Model inputs can be defined as random variables and described by a probability density function
- ▶ Probabilistic methods are used to propagate uncertainties through the models and compute variance-based sensitivities
- ▶ Estimate the contribution from aleatory (inherent variations) and epistemic (knowledge-based) uncertainty

▶ Sensitivities are dependent on...

- ▶ Strength of the correlation between the input parameter and the response
- ▶ Range of variation for the random variable in the analysis

▶ Sensitivity analysis objectives

- ▶ Elucidate relationship between mesoscale architecture and macroscale pi-joint response
- ▶ Identifying steps to reduce uncertainty in model predictions and mature the P2P framework

Latin Hypercube Sampling of Constituent Properties

Homogenization of Mesoscale Textile Model

Response Surface Model Development

Homogenized Pi-joint Model Simulations

Probabilistic Analysis

Mesoscale Textile Model⁴

Constituent Material Property	COV (%)	Number of Measurements (<i>N</i>)	Characterization Method	Layup
Matrix Tensile Modulus (E_m)	5.98	12	ASTM D638	N/A
Matrix Poisson's Ratio (ν_m)	1.66	4	ASTM D638	N/A
Tow Longitudinal Tensile Modulus ($E_{1,tow}$)	2.17	8	ASTM D3039	[0] ₈
Tow Transverse Tensile Modulus ($E_{2,tow}$)	3.16	5	ASTM D3039	[90] ₁₆
Tow XY Shear Modulus ($G_{12,tow}$)	3.80	4	non-standard PTS15	[0] ₄₈
Tow XZ Shear Modulus ($G_{13,tow}$)	1.49	6	modified ASTM D2344	[0] ₄₈
Tow YZ Shear Modulus ($G_{23,tow}$)	2.30	4	non-standard PTS15	[0] ₄₈
Tow XY Poisson's Ratio ($\nu_{12,tow}$)	8.45	3	ASTM D3039	[0] ₈
Warp Tow Fiber Volume Fraction ($V_{f,warp}$)	6.17	8	optical microscopy	N/A
Fill Tow Fiber Volume Fraction ($V_{f,fill}$)	5.14	10	optical microscopy	N/A

Macroscale Pi-joint Model⁵

Pi-joint Model Parameter Description	Parameter	Approx. COV (%)	Uncertainty Quantification
Pi-joint Geometry			
Base Thickness	tb	3	calibration
Base Taper Thickness	$tb\ taper$	5	conservative assumption
Full Base Width, including taper	$wb\ taper$	5	calibration
Leg Thickness	tl	3	calibration
Leg Taper Thickness	$tl\ taper$	5	conservative assumption
Leg Width, including taper	$wl\ taper$	4	calibration
Unitape Skin Ply Thickness	$tply\ uni$	3.75	calibration
Fabric Web Ply Thickness	$tply\ fab$	5	calibration
Unitape and Fabric Mechanical Properties			
Unitape Skin Shear Modulus G23	$G23\ u$	10	conservative assumption
Quasi-isotropic Unitape Mod. E11 Tension	$E11\ tqu$	10	calibration
Quasi-Isotropic Fabric Mod. E11 Tension	$E11\ tqf$	10	conservative assumption
Adhesive Cohesive Zone Law			
Normal Strength, Mode I	$S\ n$	20	calibration
Shear Strength, Mode II	$S\ s$	20	calibration
Mode I Strain Energy Release Rate	$G\ n$	20	calibration
Mode II Strain Energy Release Rate	$G\ s$	20	calibration
Mixed-mode Exponent	BK	10	calibration
Compliance Constant, Mode I	$alpha\ n$	20	calibration
Compliance Constant, Mode II	$alpha\ s$	20	calibration

$$COV = \frac{\text{standard deviation}}{\text{mean}}$$

[4] Kirby et al. AIAA SciTech, 2022.

[5] Kirby et al. AIAA SciTech, 2023.

Maximum Load Response

- ▶ Max load is primarily governed by **failure of the adhesive but also influenced by geometry**
- ▶ Most sensitive to the Mode I cohesive zone strength → **unexpected for a bending test**
- ▶ Of constituent properties, only sensitive to $V_{f,warp}$
 - ▶ E_1 in the leg is most sensitive to uncertainty in $V_{f,warp}$ ⁴
 - ▶ Beam theory → **bending stress is a function of E_1 in the leg**

[4] Kirby et al. AIAA SciTech, 2022.

Stiffness Response

- ▶ Stiffness is sensitive to pi-joint geometry, not adhesive failure
- ▶ Bending stiffness directly related to **fabric web thickness** and E_1 in leg
- ▶ Similar to max load, stiffness is sensitive to $V_{f,warp}$ → **significance of E_1 in leg**

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Maximum Stress Response

- ▶ Max stress in the pi-preform during LB is in the radius btwn base and leg
- ▶ Max stress is primarily sensitive to constituent properties ($V_{f,warp}$) and is also influenced by geometry
- ▶ Should pursue efforts to reduce uncertainty in $V_{f,warp}$ and tb
- ▶ Interaction btwn pi-preform fracture and adhesive failure is not captured in model

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- ▶ Can use model for max stress or max load to compare to experimental data → **reliability analysis**
 - ▶ Could compute the probability that the max stress exceeds the strength
 - ▶ Could estimate probability of pi-preform fracture vs. failure in the adhesive for pristine pi-joints
- ▶ Limited data for leg strength (5 tests) is a significant source of uncertainty → **recommend additional tests to reduce uncertainty**
- ▶ Future work → **how does predicted uncertainty using mesoscale model compare to measured uncertainty?**

- ▶ Developing a multiscale 3D textile pi-joint model to aid in design and analysis of textile architectures and investigate their impact on component performance
- ▶ Sensitivities provide an understanding of the impact of uncertainty at the constituent level on uncertainty in the predicted pi-joint response
- ▶ Limitation of the parametric pi-joint model = damage only modeled in the adhesive → global force-displacement response does not show sensitivity to constituent properties other than $V_{f,warp}$
- ▶ Future work:
 - ▶ Use separate textile models for base, leg, and transition region
 - ▶ Compare and contrast different fiber weave architectures and constituent materials (different fiber and resin)
 - ▶ Look at additional loading cases → only looked at lateral bend so far
 - ▶ Further investigation of uncertainty in fiber volume fraction → all responses sensitive to $V_{f,warp}$
- ▶ **The homogenized model approach is only one piece of the larger P2P framework that is being developed under OPPEA**